

THE ROLE OF GREEN MANUFACTURING IN ENHANCING THE GREEN COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF THE OPINIONS OF A SAMPLE OF GENERAL COMPANY FOR TEXTILE AND LEATHER INDUSTRY IN BAGHDAD

ALYAA M. SALIH¹ and QASIM N. ALWAN²

¹Business Administration Department, The College of Administration and Economics, Al Iraqia University, Baghdad, Iraq. Email: Aliyaamhmmmd@gmail.com

²Prof at Business Administration Department , the College of Administration and Economics, Al Iraqia University, Baghdad, Iraq. Email: qasim.naif1964@baghdadcollege.edu.iq

Abstract:

This research aims mainly to identify the extent of the impact of the Green Manufacturing on Green Competitive Advantage in the General Company for Textile and Leather Industry in the city of Baghdad. It was prepared to collect the necessary data, which is a research scale, and the questionnaire was distributed to a sample taken randomly according to (Stephen Thompson) equation from the research community consisting of employees in the General Company for the Textile and Leather Industry in Baghdad, where the sample size was (154), and to test the research hypotheses A set of statistical methods were adopted, and the statistical program (SPSS.V.25) and the program (SMART PLS V.3.3.9) were adopted. This research reached a set of conclusions, the most important of which are: The green manufacturing variable in its dimensions has an effective and essential impact on the green competitive advantage in the research sample company.

Keywords: Green Manufacturing, Reduce waste, Recycling, Reuse, Green energy, Green design, Green Competitive Advantage.

1. Introduction

Green awareness began in the period between the sixties and the early seventies of the last century with growing concern about the negative impact of the consumption pattern, and the impact of economic and population growth on the environment. However, an interest in linking management concepts to green aspects emerged in the late 1980s with a rapid increase in consumer awareness of green products. The growing awareness of environmentally friendly products, and their willingness to pay for these products, has led to increased interest in these products encouraging companies to show interest in green aspects (Kumar et al, 2011:622), The roots of green manufacturing go back to Germany, which requires importing companies to take responsibility and remove any packaging materials used for this product, as the Germans set a de facto global standard for manufacturing, which is that any company that wants to compete globally must start making products that comply with the green requirements of the European market (Barua & Satapath, 2015: 492).

The world witnessed an increase in social and moral awareness in the seventies of the last century at all levels due to the high rates of environmental pollution as a result of unplanned actions. Where the United Nations Environment held in the Swedish capital Stockholm (1972)

a conference known as the (Human Environment Conference) to be considered one of the foundations of the history of the development of environmental thought as an important and essential element in preserving the environment. Environmental trends in 1995 resulted in the introduction of the concept of control over The product by focusing on green processes beyond the completion of manufacturing processes and adding quality management system standards (ISO 9001, environmental management system ISO 14001) and occupational health and safety management system to support green sustainability processes (Wen et al, 2019:3), in addition Therefore, the conference organized by the United Nations (1992) for environment and development in the capital of Brazil, which was known as the Earth Summit Conference, which focused on the concept of green manufacturing globally, and which was classified among the best systems that increase the efficiency of manufacturing processes, helped.(Huiling & Dan,2020: 2).

The process of manufacturing products is a very important process in the lives of individuals, but it carries with it a lot of risks to the environment in terms of consumption of resources needed for production and pollution resulting from the manufacturing process. In 1987, the Industrial Operations Committee, which can be considered the most efficient in the use of resources and generates the least amount of pollution and waste, expected the use of renewable materials (recycling), which reduce the negative effects on human life and the environment, and this vision became the engine of the cleaner production process, which is promoted United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) since 1980.

Organizations that depend on green competitive advantage are called green organizations and assume that competitive advantage is not only achieving profits, but reducing environmental and social impacts so that future generations can have sufficient resources to meet their needs and desires Sustainable Competitiveness.

1.1 Research problem.

Industrial organizations in general, Iraqi industrial organizations in particular, faced great challenges, especially in light of a dynamic environment that threatens their competitive advantage. The required level and in a way that supports green trends, and the researcher believes that green manufacturing plays an important role in enhancing its green competitive advantage to face many challenges, including fierce competition and dependence on the importer more than the local industry, weak infrastructure, unstable security situation, lack of skills of workers, and outdated equipment, devices and buildings and other many obstacles Which makes it imperative for the company to own manufacturing that supports green trends, encourages employees to perform their work perfectly and achieve positive results that enable the company to compete locally and globally, and the current study sheds light on the role of green manufacturing in enhancing the green competitive advantage. The main problems facing the company under consideration

Therefore, the current study raises the following main question (Does green manufacturing affect the promotion of green competitive advantage in the State Company for Textile and Leather Industry?).

1.2 Research Objectives

The study mainly aims to verify the effect of green manufacturing on the green competitive advantage in the State Company for Textile and Leather Industry.

- a. The current study seeks to prepare a cognitive framework for the study variables represented by (green manufacturing, green competitive advantage) with its sub-dimensions in order to extract the conceptual and intellectual frameworks that strengthen the links between the variables.
- b. Knowing the level of awareness of green manufacturing in its dimensions (reducing waste, recycling, reusing, green manufacturing, green energy) in light of the answers of employees of the General Company for Textile and Leather Industry.
- c. .Diagnosing the level of green competitive advantage with its dimensions (green creativity, green cost, green quality, green products, green management) according to the answers of employees of the General Company for Textile and Leather Industry.
- d. Testing the influence relationship between green manufacturing and green competitive advantage in the State Company for Textile and Leather Industry.

2-Theoretical framework for research

2.1 The concept of Green Manufacturing

The term "green", often used interchangeably with "environmentally safe", comes from an ideology originally developed by the Green Party, a political party in Australia in the early 1970s whose political agenda spread rapidly across the world. Their name has been assimilated into the North American vernacular significantly (Miller et al, 2010: 12).

(Malhotra & Kumarm, 2017: 300) defined Green Manufacturing as a method of producing goods and services with limited impacts on the environment in light of the current technological and economic challenges, while (Avancini et al, 2019: 2) defined green manufacturing as a systematic approach to eliminating waste, optimizing the use and selection of resources and technologies, thereby minimizing the impact on the environment. (Mutubuki & Chirinda, 2020: 1) is a system that integrates product design and process design aspects that affect production, planning and control in order to identify, measure, evaluate and manage the flow of environmental waste, with the goal of minimizing waste, maximizing resource use and minimizing impact Negative to the environment (Pei et al, 2021:304) is a modern manufacturing framework that comprehensively considers its environmental impact and resource efficiency.

The researcher defined green manufacturing was a method of production followed by some industrial companies that seek to reduce waste, recycling, use of products, use of green energy and green design in order to achieve a green competitive advantage.

2.2 Measuring of Green Manufacturing

Green Manufacturing can be measured through the following dimensions;

- a. **Reduce waste:** Source reduction includes changes in product specifications to accommodate design for the environment, changes in products and raw materials, changes in production processes and investment in cost-reduction techniques, when resource reduction is improved. A source reduction strategy, in the name of waste prevention, is the most environmentally preferable strategy. Source reduction generally refers to any action that results in a net reduction in solid waste generation at the source (Giri & Singh, 2018: 234).
- b. **Recycling**“Although material recycling is the most widely used strategy to avoid waste for the environment rather than transport it to a landfill, many designers are reluctant to use recycled components due to the uncertainty in performance and quality parameters. However, from another point of view Purchasing recycled products provides immediate savings because these materials are cheaper than their counterparts (Almeida, 2014: 189).
- c. **Reuse:** The Environment and Water Research Unit believes that the reuse and recycling of solid waste contribute to preserving the environment and reducing pollution, such as: Protecting the environment from harmful chemicals: that can result from the decomposition of materials that are buried in sanitary landfills and providing the energy needed for manufacturing, because the manufacture of raw materials needs To large amounts of energy, in contrast to recyclable materials, reducing the amount of materials reaching sanitary landfills, and extending the life of these sites to accommodate non-recyclable waste (Abualfaraa et al, 2020: 4).
- d. **Green energy:**Energy efficiency is measured by comparing energy used versus goods produced. It is better to have more output from the energy saved through improved operation of power systems and processes and this translates to cost savings through reduced energy loss. Energy efficiency can be achieved through innovation of new heating technology. Improving energy efficiency can provide economic, social and environmental benefits to the economy (Eshikumo, 2017:3).
- e. **Green design** Most industrial companies desire to produce low-pollution and environmentally friendly products that meet the needs and desires of the customer or exceed their expectations, in order to reach the so-called (green customer), which is the consumer who is environmentally conscious and who manages his business mainly based on the principles he believes in and that push him to avoid buying products with Negative impact on society and the environment The green product is seen as causing minor damage because it is designed, manufactured, marketed and sold to consumers in environmentally friendly ways that reduce the negative environmental impacts resulting from it. Costs, process improvement and material reuse (Vervliet, 2916: 14).

2.3 The concept of Green Competitive Advantage

Green competitive advantage is a situation in which organizations occupy many positions in relation to environmental protection or green innovation, and competitors cannot imitate a successful environmental strategy, which leads to the organization obtaining sustainable benefits from this environmental strategy. Organizations in the field of environmental

innovation can gain a competitive advantage, and was able to sell its technology or environmental services to improve the organization's image and create new markets (Astuti & Datrini, 2021:4) (Reginald, 2010, 6) Defined green competitive advantage, which is the organization's ability to achieve rates of return more than its normal averages, which creates an advantage competitiveness of the organization, and (Male et al.,2015:74) defined is the superiority over others using the strategy of orientation towards the customer and the optimal use of resources, and, (Gomes & Romão, 2019: 1420) defined as having rare resources that are difficult to copy and imitate by others.

Researcher defined green competitive advantage is a method in Production is followed by some industrial companies that seek to produce a unique production that seeks to reduce waste, recycle, reuse, use green energy and green design in order to achieve a green competitive advantage.

2.4 Measuring the green competitive advantage

It is possible to clarify the most important dimensions of the green competitive advantage, which will be addressed in this research;

- a. **Green creativity:** Creativity is one of the most important advantages through which the organization can offer new products and services and develop existing products and services, through which costs can be reduced by using alternatives of raw materials, products and services of high quality and speed of response to market changes in providing new products and services commensurate with the customer's desires to continue (Roschangar et al, 2018: 3).
- b. **Green cost:** Operations management often seeks to reduce costs by reducing fixed costs, exercising continuous control over raw materials, reducing wage rates, and achieving high levels of productivity. . Attar, (58, 2010).
- c. **Green quality:**For the purpose of industrial organizations to remain in the competitive market, they must provide a high quality product that meets the ambition and desire of customers. Therefore, the concept of quality is one of the concepts that have received great attention from researchers in the field of operations management. The intangible aspects made it a prerequisite for the success of the organization (Ndarajah, 2013:54).
- d. **Green products:** Green products are meant to respond to the requirements and needs of the environment and are characterized by being recyclable, recyclable and repairable. They respond to the green needs of customers and consumer rights protection associations. Green products are less polluting to the environment, less use of hazardous materials and an environmental cost (pride & Ferrell, 2007: 91).
- e. **Green management:** Green management can be referred to as the behaviors of managers who motivate followers to achieve environmental goals and inspire workers to perform beyond the expected levels of environmental performance. Moreover, green management can be measured, and it includes developing green products, building environmental plans, developing green products, a clear environmental vision, working

to achieve the same environmental goals, encouraging workers to achieve environmental goals, taking into account environmental beliefs, and motivating them to think about green ideas (Chen & Chang, 2013 : 112).

2.5 Hypotheses and Research Model

2.5.1 Research Model

2.5.2 Research Hypotheses

The first hypothesis (H1): “There is a significant effect of Green Manufacturing and its dimensions on the Green Competitive Advantage from the point of view of the research sample members.

The second hypothesis (H2): “there is a significant effect of the combined dimensions of Green Manufacturing on the Green Competitive Advantage in the research sample members.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Community and sample research

The research community consisted of employees in the General Company for the Textile and Leather Industry in the city of Baghdad, their number was (170) individuals, and a random sample of (154) individuals was selected, the sample was chosen on the basis of (Steven's equation).

3.2 Evaluating the quality and conformity of the used metrics in the research

3.2.1 Assessment of the quality and conformity of the Green Manufacturing variable questions

Table (1) shows the external saturations and the Facronbach coefficient for the questions of the green manufacturing variable, which consists of five basic dimensions and consists of (32) items, as the model will be tested within the following indicators: Table (1) shows the (CR)

values of the green manufacturing variable, which are all within the acceptable limits, as they ranged between (0.909-0.952), which is a good indicator and indicates the stability of the scale, as the results showed a high stability of the dimensions of the green manufacturing variable scale.

Table (1): Statistical indicators of the green manufacturing variable

Dimensions	Questions	Saturates	Standard error	Alpha Cronbach	compound Reliability CR	Average variance Extract(AVE)
Reduce waste	Q1	0.800	0.046	0.879	0.909	0.625
	Q2	0.801	0.043			
	Q3	0.739	0.048			
	Q4	0.676	0.071			
	Q5	0.849	0.021			
	Q6	0.862	0.022			
Recycling	W1	0.792	0.041	0.919	0.937	0.713
	W2	0.879	0.019			
	W3	0.897	0.017			
	W4	0.815	0.033			
	W5	0.809	0.042			
	W6	0.869	0.023			
Reuse	R1	0.833	0.031	0.939	0.952	0.767
	R2	0.898	0.023			
	R3	0.834	0.036			
	R4	0.863	0.027			
	R5	0.912	0.013			
	R6	0.912	0.015			
Green energy	A1	0.735	0.049	0.936	0.948	0.724
	A2	0.850	0.025			
	A3	0.830	0.034			
	A4	0.852	0.025			
	A5	0.876	0.024			
	A6	0.913	0.017			
	A7	0.888	0.019			
Green design	C1	0.787	0.034	0.912	0.930	0.656
	C2	0.809	0.032			
	C3	0.790	0.036			
	C4	0.796	0.035			
	C5	0.855	0.023			
	C6	0.830	0.025			
	C7	0.799	0.034			

Source: SmartPls V.3.3.9 program

- Through the value of Alpha Cronbach's coefficient, as their results ranged between (0.879-0.939), it is clear that it is greater than (0.70), and this indicates that the validity and reliability coefficient of the measurement tool has a high degree of stability.

- It appears through the values of the external saturation (OL) of the scale questions for the variable (green manufacturing) is close to greater than the acceptable minimum limits of (0.70), as the values of external saturation ranged between (0.676-0.913), which indicates that the data for the manufacturing variable Green is characterized by stability and internal consistency and is suitable for conducting subsequent statistical analyzes, as all of them exceeded the significant values of saturation, which is a good indicator. It should be noted here that some of the questions had ramifications less than (0.70) and because they were significant, and when they were deleted, the researcher found that they did not affect the validity of the model, and based on this result, it was kept within the model.

- Table (1) shows the values of the extracted average variance (AVE) for the green manufacturing variable, as it is clear that all of them are acceptable, as they ranged between (0.625-0.767), which is greater than the value (0.50), which all indicates the convergent validity of the dimensions, which is a good indicator.

- It is clear from the table (1) that all parameter estimates were significant for the questions of the green manufacturing variable, as the calculated T-Value, which ranges between (9.52-67.85), is greater than its tabular value, which amounts to (1.984), as it is also evident from the value of (P-Value, which is (0.000) for all questions, is less than (0.05), as it indicates that all questions were significant.

3.2.2 Assessment of the quality and conformity of green competitive advantage variable questions

Table (2) shows the external saturations and the Cronbach coefficient for the questions of the green competitive advantage variable, which consists of five basic dimensions and consists of (28) paragraphs, as the model will be tested within the following indicators:

- Table (2) shows the composite stability values (CR) for the green competitive advantage variable, which were collected within the acceptable limits and ranged between (0.924-0.968), which is a good indicator, as the results showed a high stability of the research scale questions for the green competitive advantage variable.

- The results showed that the value of the Alpha Cronbach coefficient ranged between (0.898-0.962), and it is clear that it is greater than (0.70), and this indicates that the validity and reliability coefficient of the measurement tool has a high degree of acceptance and stability.

- It appears through the values of the external saturations of the scale questions for the variable (green competitive advantage), as its values ranged between (0.767-0.921), which indicates that the questions of the green competitive advantage variable are characterized by stability and internal consistency and are suitable for conducting subsequent statistical analyzes.

- Table (2) shows the values of the extracted average variance (AVE) for the green competitive advantage variable, as it is clear that all of them are acceptable, as they ranged between (0.673-0.813), which is greater than the value (0.50), as they all indicate the convergent validity of the dimensions, which is a good indicator

- It is clear from the table (2) that all the parameter estimates were significant for the questions of the green competitive advantage variable, as the calculated T-Value, which ranged between (16,439- 60.17), is greater than its tabular value, which amounted to (1.984), as well as the value of (P- Value), whose values are (0.000), which is less than (0.05), and it indicates that all questions were significant, which is a good indicator.

Table (2) Statistical indicators of the variable Green Competitive Advantage

Dimensions	Questions	Saturates	Standard error	Alpha Cronbach	compound Reliability CR	Average variance Extract(AVE)
Green creativity	V1	0.783	0.045	0.913	0.935	0.742
	V2	0.898	0.015			
	V3	0.861	0.027			
	V4	0.883	0.021			
	V5	0.878	0.023			
	B1	0.777	0.044			
Green cost	B2	0.802	0.049	0.903	0.925	0.673
	B3	0.838	0.030			
	B4	0.820	0.032			
	B5	0.845	0.027			
	B6	0.840	0.026			
	N1	0.852	0.028			
Green quality	N2	0.872	0.027	0.920	0.940	0.758
	N3	0.891	0.018			
	N4	0.861	0.027			
	N5	0.875	0.021			
	H1	0.767	0.045			
	H2	0.879	0.022			
Green products	H3	0.810	0.037	0.898	0.924	0.710
	H4	0.880	0.020			
	H5	0.872	0.021			
	K1	0.836	0.034			
	K2	0.905	0.019			
	K3	0.901	0.021			
	K4	0.920	0.015			
Green management	K5	0.907	0.020	0.962	0.968	0.813
	K6	0.919	0.017			
	K7	0.921	0.016			
	V1	0.783	0.045			
	V2	0.898	0.015			
	V3	0.861	0.027			
	V4	0.883	0.021			

Source: SmartPls V.3.3.9 program

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Statistical analysis of the variables:

Table (3) shows the search variables in general as follows: -

- As the results showed that the highest value was at the variable (green competitive advantage) with an arithmetic mean (3.531), a good level and a standard deviation (0.812), as its coefficient of variation reached (22,996), as the percentage of availability of the variable in the surveyed factories in general was (70.62%). As for the size of the gap, it reached (29.38%), as this variable came at the first level in terms of relative importance.

- As for the lowest value, it came at the variable (green manufacturing) with an arithmetic mean (3.314) and a good level with a standard deviation of (0.807), as its coefficient of variation reached (24,351), as the percentage of availability of the variable in the factories surveyed in general was (66.28%) as for the size of the gap It reached (33.72 percent), as this variable came in the second level in terms of relative importance.

- It is clear that the variable (green competitive advantage) came first in terms of research variables, as most of the sample answers were in agreement about this variable compared to the other variable.

Table (3): Summary of the dimensions of the research variables

S/N	Research variables	mean	Standard deviation	coefficient variation	Availability percentage	Size of the gap	Order of variables
1	Green Manufacturing	3.314	0.807	24.351	66.28	33.72	1
2	Green Competitive Advantage	3.531	0.812	22.996	70.62	29.38	2

Source: SPSS V.25 program

4.2 Hypothesis testing between the dimensions of Green Manufacturing in the Green Competitive Advantage

4.2.1 First hypothesis test:

Which states that (there is no significant effect between the green manufacturing variable on the green competitive advantage)

Table (4) indicates the statistical indicators for testing the hypotheses between the green manufacturing variable in the green competitive advantage.

- The calculated (t) value of the estimated model achieved its value (33.481). And it is greater than the tabular value (t) of (1.984) at the level of significance (0.05), and this indicates the significance of the marginal slope of the green manufacturing variable. In light of this result, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis that (there is a significant

effect between the green manufacturing variable in the green competitive advantage), and this indicates that the green manufacturing variable has an effective and essential effect on the green competitive advantage.

- The results indicated that the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the green manufacturing variable was (0.833), and this indicates that an increase in the green manufacturing variable by one unit will lead to an increase in (the green competitive advantage) by (83%).
- The results showed that the effect size (f2) for the green manufacturing variable was large, as it recorded a value of (2.258), which is greater than (0.35), which is a good indicator.
- It is clear through the value of the Adjusted Determination Coefficient (R^2) of (0.691) that the green manufacturing variable is able to explain 69% of the changes that occur in (green competitive advantage), while the remaining percentage (31%) is dependent on other variables other than included in the search form.
- The results showed that the predictive relationship index (Q^2) for the green manufacturing variable reached a value of (0.376), which is greater than zero, and accordingly, the model has a predictive relationship.

Table (4): Statistical indicators between green manufacturing and green competitive advantage

Green Manufacturing	B	T	Values P	effect size f2	Impact strength	(R2)	Adjusted (R2)	Q ²	VIF
	0.833	33.481	0.000	2.258	Great	0.693	0.691	0.376	1

Tabular t = 1.984, sample size = 154

Source: SmartPls V.3.3.9 program.

Figure (2): the effect between the Green manufacturing in Green competitive advantage

Source: SmartPls V.3.3.9 program

4.2.2 Testing the second hypothesis:

Test the second main hypothesis that (there is a significant effect between the dimensions of green manufacturing together on the green competitive advantage), as the table () shows the statistical indicators between the dimensions of green manufacturing in the green competitive advantage as follows:

- It is evident through the value of the (t) test for the dimensions of green manufacturing that the dimensions (reduce waste, green energy, green design) whose values are (4.398, 5.153, 3.916) respectively, are greater than the tabular (t) value of (1.984), and this indicates To prove the significance of the marginal tendency of the dimensions (reduce waste, green energy, green design), while the other dimensions represented by the dimensions (recycling, reuse) are shown by the calculated (t) value of (1.202, 0.447) that it is less than the value of (t.) tabulation amounting to (1.984), and this indicates that the marginal slope of the two dimensions (recycling, reuse) was not significant.
- It is evident from the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the waste reduction dimension of (0.295) that an increase after reducing waste by one unit will lead to an increase in (the green competitive advantage) by (29%).
- It appears through the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the green energy dimension of (0.389) that an increase in the green energy dimension by one unit will lead to an increase in the (green competitive advantage) by (38%).
- It is clear from the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the green design dimension of (0.265) that an increase in the green design dimension by one unit will lead to an increase in (the green competitive advantage) by (26%).
- It is evident through the value of the Adjusted Determination Coefficient (R^2) of (0.727) that the dimensions of green manufacturing are able to explain about (72%) of the changes that occur in (the green competitive advantage), while the remaining percentage (28%) is dependent on other variables than included in the search form.
- The results showed that the predictive relationship index (Q^2) reached a value of (0.397), which is greater than zero, and accordingly, the model has a predictive relationship.
- The results showed that the variance inflation factor (VIF) achieved its value (2.109, 3.678, 3.411, 2.689, 2.191) respectively, which is less than (5) and indicates that there is no problem of multi-linearity between dimensions.
- The results showed that the most influential dimension in the green competitive advantage was after the green energy, as the effect size for it was (0.213) and with an average effect strength.
- The results showed that the least effect on the green competitive advantage was after re-use, as the effect size was (0.011) with a weak impact strength.

Table (5): Statistical indicators between the dimensions of green manufacturing together in the green competitive advantage

dimensions of green manufacturing	B	T	P Values	Effect size f2	(R2)	Adjusted (R2)	Q ²
Reduce waste	0.295	4.398	0.000	0.156	0.729	0.718	0.327
Recycling	0.103	1.202	0.230	0.011			
Reuse	-0.036	0.447	0.655	0.001			
Green energy	0.389	5.153	0.000	0.213			
Green design	0.265	3.916	0.000	0.121			

Tabular t = 1.984, sample size = 154

Source: SmartPls V.3.3.9 program.

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

5.1 Conclusions

It was concluded that the company uses many materials in packaging and does not place it as returning the products after use, which increases the chances of environmental pollution, The research concluded that the General Company for Textile and Leather Industry seeks to reduce waste resulting from production processes, and adopts the method of recycling defective products to preserve the environment, It turns out that the General Company for Textile and Leather Industry does not manufacture reusable products, but rather produces products that are used once. The company does not seek to use green energy continuously, but rather resorts to saving energy as much as possible to reduce costs, There is little interest from the company's management in the field of application in parts that can be used in other products, and a good concern about reducing toxic and hazardous materials as much as possible, It turns out that the company's management is concerned with the dimension of waste reduction mainly, followed by green design, green energy and recycling, while after reuse it ranked last within the dimensions of the green manufacturing variable at the company level, the field of application, The administrations working in the factories and laboratories of the General Company for the Textile and Leather Industry practice limited encouragement for self-learning for the two years and openness to others' experiences by the company's management, as well as raising their skills to reduce labor costs, It was concluded that the company's management is working continuously to improve and develop the products it offers, as well as its keenness to provide the goods at the lowest price and the best possible quality and strive to increase the market share, It turns out that the company's management in the field of application depends slightly on the manufacture of recyclable products and seeks to take more care towards environmental responsibility with less health damage to the customer and encourages workers to achieve this, It was found from the study that the factories and laboratories of the State Company for the Textile and Leather Industry were concerned with the green quality variable in the first place, followed by green creativity, green cost and green products, and green management ranked last within the dimensions of green competitive advantage, It was concluded that green manufacturing causes a change in the green competitive advantage of the company. The field of application at the level of variables and their dimensions in the current study.

5.2. Future Suggestions

Conducting a study with the same variables and their dimensions in a different industrial environment that was in the field of food industries or in the service environment such as education or the banking sector and comparing the results with the current study to study the possibility of generalizing the results in the Iraqi environment.

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